

Experimental Analysis of Photovoltaic Module Performance based on Ambient Temperature, Module Temperature and Dust Accumulation

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Abstract

In recent years, the shift in interest from fossil fuel-based power generation to renewable energy has led to a significant increase in the use of photovoltaic (PV) technology. Therefore, studying its performance is a priority in research in the solar energy field. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is notable for its vast area and contemporaneous climate change. The current study analyzes the combined effects of ambient temperature, module temperature and dust accumulation on the efficiency of solar modules. To achieve this goal, an experimental set-up was conducted at three different locations in different cities within the kingdom. These cities are Al-Jubail, Jeddah and Al-Baha. As a result, it was found that dust accumulation adversely affected the performance of solar panels. As the ambient temperature increases, the temperature of the solar module increases. Additionally, elevated ambient temperatures adversely affect solar panels, leading to reduced efficiency. Increasing the temperature of the solar panel will reduce its efficiency. The results also showed that different geographical locations had different influence rates for these parameters.

Keywords: PV module; solar panel efficiency; solar energy; dust accumulation.

Nomenclature

Symbol	Definition	Unit
T_{mt}	Calculated PV module temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
T_{ma}	Measured PV module temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
T_{amb}	Ambient temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
η	Solar panel efficiency	-
P_{in}	Input power	W
P_{max}	Maximum output power	W
E	Incident radiation flux	W/m^2
A_c	Area of PV panel	m^2
t	Measuring time	hour
η	The efficiency	--

1. Introduction

Photovoltaic (PV) module technology is the most important part of solar energy technology for energy generation [1]. Solar modules have a variety of applications for power generation in remote, rural and even urban areas [2]. They have many uses, from agricultural and domestic industries. PV modules can be used in most applications that require solar energy. Solar modules can be used in buildings for his dual purpose of generating electricity and generating thermal energy. Such systems are known as Building Integrated Photovoltaic Thermal (BIPVT) systems. BIPVT systems have numerous domestic and industrial applications [3, 4]. Regarding renewable energy sources, photovoltaic (PV) technology, which converts sunlight into electricity, is becoming increasingly popular, especially in countries with abundant sunlight. In recent years, PV has shown a lot of growth and new ideas. Technologies manufactured by different companies are starting to develop and they are different. For each type of PV module, there are many things to know. Manufacturers provide information on typical power rating parameters [5]. PV technologies operating in warm climates have module temperatures well above 25°C , which is a very important factor in performance degradation. A parameter that describes the operating temperature and thermal effects of PV electrical properties is the temperature coefficient [6]. The temperature of a photovoltaic module directly affects its power generation capacity. This effect is reflected in the temperature coefficient. The temperature coefficient is expressed as the percentage decrease in performance for each 1 degree Celsius ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) temperature increase from 25°C . The temperature coefficient of most photovoltaic modules

is around $-0.3\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $-0.5\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$. In a country like Saudi Arabia, with abundant solar resources and a mild climate, the impact of temperature on photovoltaic technologies is an important selection criterion. A study to assess the effect of temperature was performed using indoor and outdoor methods [7]. The purpose of the current study was to investigate the effects of ambient temperature, PV module temperature, and dust accumulation on PV module performance. Current experimental setup is conducted underway in three cities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA): Al-Jubail, Jeddah and Al-Baha.

2. Theoretical analysis

This section details a theoretical method for calculating the efficiency and temperature of a PV module. This theoretical analysis serves to compare the experimental data of the current study.

2.1 PV module efficiency

By using equations (2) and (3) that represent simple solar module efficiency, the efficiency of a solar panel is calculated.

$$\eta_{max} = \frac{P_{max}}{E \cdot A_c} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where:

P_{in} : power input, (W)

P_{max} : Maximum power output, (W)

E : Incident radiation flux, (W/m^2)

A_c : Area of PV panel, (m^2)

$$P_{max} = V_{oc} \cdot I_{sc} \cdot FF \quad (3)$$

Where:

V_{oc} : the open-circuit voltage

I_{sc} : the short-circuit current

FF: the fill factor

η : the efficiency

2.2 PV module temperature

PV module temperature simulation using nominal operating cell temperature (NOCT) is widely used to easily measure the annual module performance. In this context, it is important to ensure that this parameter is determined. This is because it is used to compare the performance of different module designs and can affect system predictions. Module temperature can be calculated from

ambient temperature, available solar radiation and NOCT. Temperature module formula [8]:

$$T_{mt} = T_{amb} + (NOCT - 20) \frac{E}{800} \quad (4)$$

Where T_{mt} is the module temperature, T_{amb} is the ambient temperature and E is the irradiance in W/m^2 . This equation is widely used to estimate in a simple way module temperature along the year. After knowing the theoretical module temperature the deviation percentage about its value can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Deviation percentage} = \frac{T_{ma} - T_{mt}}{T_{mt}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

This deviation is a good tool to compare the present work experimental results.

2.3 Temperature coefficient of PV module

The temperature of a photovoltaic panel directly affects the amount of power it can generate. This is reflected in the temperature coefficient, which indicates the rate at which performance degrades for every $25^{\circ}C$ increase in temperature of 1 degree Celsius ($^{\circ}C$) [9]. The tests are conducted to see how well the photovoltaic modules perform at the standard test conditions (STC) cell temperature of $25^{\circ}C$. It is important to expect 1% power loss for every $2^{\circ}C$ temperature rise above $25^{\circ}C$. Most photovoltaic panels have temperature coefficients in the ranges from -0.3% to -0.5% per degree Celsius. This means that as the temperature rises, the coefficient goes down [1].

3. Experimental setup

Figure (1) schematically shows the experimental set-up for this study performed at three different locations. The first location is Al-Jubail city in eastern Saudi Arabia. The second location is the city of Jeddah in the west. Finally, there is the city of Al-Baha, located in the southwest of Saudi Arabia. The longitude and latitude coordinates of these locations are $27.13N$ $49.534E$, $21.766N$ $39.199E$, and $20.518N$ $41.665E$ respectively. The current working setup consists of a TPS-12-5 solar PV module facing the sun and an Arduino Uno board microcontroller attached to it. Also, two types of temperature sensors are used to measure ambient temperature and module temperature. The LM35 temperature sensor is used to measure ambient temperature. Here we measure the temperature of the PV module using the DS18B20 waterproof temperature sensor. An LCD screen displays these measurements using a microcontroller

Figure (1): General Schematic view for the present work experimental

4. Results and discussion

The study in this section analyzes the consequences of the effects of ambient temperature and PV module temperature, in addition to the effect of dust accumulation on solar module performance. Figure (2) shows the deviation of experimentally measured values of PV module temperature from the theoretical values calculated from equation (5). The deviation appears to be between -12% and 15%. This total deviation is taken as acceptable for the current experimental results and indicates a small difference between the theoretical value and the current experimental measurements.

Figure (2): Error percentage with measuring time for all locations

Figure (3) shows the effect of dust accumulation on PV modules. An experimental simulation of dust accumulation was performed by adding a layer of dust to the solar panel. In general, it is clear that dust accumulation adversely affects the performance of solar panels. In Al-Jubail

city, the efficiency variation appears to be between 10% and 13% without dust, but decreases to 9% to 10% with dust. In Jeddah city, there is a variation of 8% to 8.5% without dust and 5% to 6% with dust. Finally, in Al-Baha city, the efficiency is 8% to 8.2% without dust and 3% to 5% with dust. This generally reflects the negative impact of dust accumulation on PV module performance. Also note that panel efficiency varies by region, with Al-Jubail in the foreground, followed by Jeddah, Al-Baha.

Figure (3): Variation of efficiency with measuring time for the present work locations

Figure (4) shows the relationship between ambient temperature and solar cell module temperature. From this figure, it is clear that the ambient temperature is directly proportional to the PV module temperature, regardless of geographical location.

Figure (4): Effect of ambient temperature on PV module temperature

Figures (5) and (6) show the effect of ambient temperature and PV module temperature on PV module performance. In all the sites where the current work was done show the negative performance impact of increasing them. These trends in our current work are compatible with previous work [11, 12].

Figure (5): Effect of ambient temperature on PV module efficiency

Figure (6): Effect of PV module temperature on PV module efficiency

Since the effect of different parameters in PV module performance from figure (3) to figure (6) are in the same direction, but at different rates, so it was necessary to clarify the difference in each geographic location in the present work. This is achieved by fitting the data to show the different rates in each location. Table (1) shows the equations resulting from fitting the data resulting from the current work and shown in Figures (3) to (6). From this table, it appears that the geographical location has a great effect on the performance of the panel. From this view, Al-Jubail is on the fore then Al-Baha and in the rear is Jeddah. Also, the relation of the ambient temperature and module temperature is directly proportional. The rate of increase in this relation is Jeddah, Al-Jubail and Al-Baha respectively. The increase of the ambient temperature has a negative effect on the module efficiency. Jeddah and Al-Baha are at the same rate of decrease in performance and Al-Jubail is more affected. Finally, from the influence of the increase of module temperature, the performance decrease from Jeddah, Al-Jubail to Al-Baha, respectively.

Table (1): Fitting equations of present work measured data

Figure no.	Fitting equation	Location
Figure (3) (a)	$\eta = 0.0011 * t + 0.0867$	Al-Jubail city without dust
Figure (3) (a)	$\eta = 0.0008 * t + 0.0800$	Al-Jubail city with dust
Figure (3) (b)	$\eta = -0.0012 * t + 0.1001$	Jeddah city without dust
Figure (3) (b)	$\eta = 0.0008 * t + 0.0424$	Jeddah city with dust
Figure (3) (c)	$\eta = 0.0003 * t + 0.0789$	Al-Baha city without dust
Figure (3) (c)	$\eta = -0.0021 * t + 0.0676$	Al-Baha city with dust
Figure (4) (a)	$T_{ma} = 1.283 * T_{amb} - 2.7082$	Al-Jubail city
Figure (4) (b)	$T_{ma} = 2.463 * T_{amb} - 25.5792$	Jeddah city
Figure (4) (c)	$T_{ma} = 0.885 * T_{amb} + 2.5895$	Al-Baha city
Figure (5) (a)	$\eta = -0.0013 * T_{amb} + 0.1163$	Al-Jubail city
Figure (5) (b)	$\eta = -0.0005 * T_{amb} + 0.0997$	Jeddah city
Figure (5) (c)	$\eta = -0.0005 * T_{amb} + 0.0902$	Al-Baha city
Figure (6) (a)	$\eta = -0.0005 * T_{ma} + 0.1049$	Al-Jubail city
Figure (6) (b)	$\eta = -0.0002 * T_{ma} + 0.0932$	Jeddah city
Figure (6) (c)	$\eta = -0.0008 * T_{ma} + 0.0971$	Al-Baha city

5. Conclusions

The current work investigates the effects of ambient temperature and PV module temperature, in addition to dust accumulation, on solar module performance at three different locations in different cities within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: Al-Jubail, Jeddah, and Al-Baha. Experimental results showed that:

- 1- Dust accumulation adversely affects the performance of solar panels.
- 2- As the ambient temperature increases, the temperature of the solar panel increases.
- 3- Increased ambient temperature adversely affects solar panels, reducing their efficiency.
- 4- Increasing the temperature of the solar panel will reduce its efficiency.
- 5- The rate of these effects depends on the geographical location

The present work shows a good compatibility with the previous work. Also, the current research opens the door on how to overcome the factors that lead to a decrease in the performance of the solar panel, whether by trying to remove dust periodically from the panel or trying to cool it by different methods.

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